

Enrichment plot: JENNEM2CDD10NM48HRUP

Enrichment plot: FORGACSF1E112H10NMTCCDDUP

Enrichment plot: JENNEM48HR10NMTCCDDOWN

Enrichment plot: FORGACSF1E1148H10NMTCCDDOWN

Enrichment plot: JENNEM12HEEVSDMSIJSOUP

Enrichment plot: JENNEM12HEEVSDMSIJSODOWN

Rank-rank Analysis

Heat map graph

Rank-rank Analysis

Heat map graph

